

FACTORS FORMING THE DISCOURSE CONTENT OF THE MAXIM OF SYMPATHY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10816952>

Absrtact. In this article the analysis of politeness is based on the sympathy maxim proposes by Leech. He proposed six types of politeness maxim. The discussion shows that communicators use all types of maxim in their conversation. Sympathy maxim is a maxim in which a speaker minimizes antipathy between self and other; maximizes sympathy between self and other. This includes a small group of speech acts such as congratulation, commiseration, and expressing condolences.

Keywords: the sympathy maxim, speech acts, congratulation, commiseration.

Pragmatics is a study of language in its relation to language use and how the language is used by its speaker in their interaction in the speech community. Pragmatics also studies the language in its context and the relation between language and context that are grammaticalized, or encoded in the structure of a language. The context in this case can be the context of situation or context of culture. Pragmatics is very important because it gives people the skills to behave in society so that in its development many people developed some theory of pragmatics to support their skills in communicating.

One of them is Geoffrey Leech with his Politeness Principles (PP) theory. According to Leech, Politeness Principle is minimizing the expression of impolite beliefs, and there is a corresponding positive version or maximizing the expression of polite beliefs which is somewhat less important. Leech proposed it to produce and understand language based on politeness. The purpose of Politeness principles itself is to establish feeling of community and social relationship. Further, Leech proposed six maxims, namely Tact Maxim, Generosity Maxim, Approbation Maxim, Modesty Maxim, Agreement Maxim, and Sympathy Maxim.

Politeness becomes an important aspect in the society; it is used to recognize social-culture within a community in a region. It means that politeness can also be regarded as some kind of social norm determined by the convention of the community. Sometimes, they have to be polite in order to show that they are civilized people and they will not be accused as rude people who have bad manner. Even though politeness can be used to recognize social-culture, in many ways, it is a universal norm. Politeness is a branch and one of the major topics of pragmatic study.

According to [Geoffrey Leech](#), there is a [politeness](#) principle with [conversational maxims](#) similar to those formulated by [Paul Grice](#). He lists six maxims: tact, generosity, approbation, modesty, agreement, and sympathy. The first and second form a pair, as do the third and the fourth. These maxims vary from [culture](#) to culture: what may be considered polite in one culture may be strange or downright rude in another.

The maxim of sympathy is one of the six maxims proposed by Leech (1983) in his PP (politeness principle). The sympathy maxim states: "minimize antipathy between self and other; maximize sympathy between the self and other". The sympathy maxim is a politeness principle that includes speech acts such as congratulation, commiseration, and expressing condolences.

Politeness is a combination of linguistic and non-linguistic behaviors that show that people take others' feelings into account.

There are different ways to realize politeness with different standards in different cultures too. One way to be polite is the use of certain polite formulas which help having good and healthy relationships with the members of the community. For instance, greeting people when you see them and inquiring about their family and work, complimenting a friend about his promotion, congratulating new married couple, thanking someone for his help, are all polite acts. To express all these social events, the speaker uses what we call “ready-made” polite forms which are at the speaker’s disposal if needed. These fixed polite formulas are studied under what is called linguapragmatics, which is defined as the: “study of the fixed forms of language that have fixed sociopragmatic values in actual verbal communication.” Such forms are different from all other forms of language in their translatability, politeness and other features.

Lingua-pragmatics is a term coined by Shamma (1995). The forms studied under linguapragmatics are used for maintaining social ties, recognizing social distance and keeping to the scale of culture-specific politeness in interpersonal interaction. These forms reflect the attitude of S towards H as well as the norms prevailing in S’s speech community and by using these forms, the speaker could always politely contradict, interrupt or even blame any of the communicators in his community; not using one of these forms might lead to a pragmatic failure.

By the way of conclusion, this paper reveals that the concept of sympathy in English has semantic properties. We claim that in genetically unrelated languages the conceptual metaphors of sympathy demonstrate common mental models and mainly vary in their verbal form and in their frequency in communication.

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